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STUDY OF CFRP PI-BEAM PARAMETRIC AND STRENGTH ANALYSIS

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Introduction

■ Background

- CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic) is a composite material made of carbon fiber and resin
- This is higher specific strength than ordinary metals and is light in weight
- CFRP has the prominent disadvantage due to its delamination
 - * **Delamination** : The phenomenon of separation between laminated fibers
- Industrial application ratio is increasing, so it is necessary to prevent delamination
 - > It is possible to prevent delamination by using 3D-structured composite material (3D preform) woven in the direction of fiber laminating

CFRP

Delamination

Beam Structure

Air craft spar

■ Purpose

- CFRP π -beam parameter optimization through finite element analysis
- Present optimal design method of 3D preform π -beam

Details

- T1, T2, and L are selected as π -beam parameters according to fiber arrangement

Details

▣ π -beam finite element analysis parameter setting

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Case 6
Support Part Ply(T1)	1	2	3	4	5	6
Base Part Ply(T2)	12	10	8	6	4	2
T1:T2 Ratio	1:13	1:6	1:3.7	1:2.5	1:1.8	1:1.3
Support Part Length (L)	30 mm		40 mm		50 mm	

▪ Analysis tool

- ANSYS ACP(Ansys Composites Prespost)

▪ Material

- Matrix : Vinly Ester
- Reinforcement : Carbon Fabric UD

	E_x	E_y	E_z	G_{xy}	G_{yz}	G_{xz}
Vinyl Ester-Carbon UD (GPa)	10.5	7.2	7.2	4.7	3.1	4.7

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Property	Value	Unit		
2	Density	1.49E-09	mm ⁻³ t		
3	Orthotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion				
8	Orthotropic Elasticity				
9	Young's Modulus X direction	10539	MPa		
10	Young's Modulus Y direction	7247	MPa		
11	Young's Modulus Z direction	7247	MPa		
12	Poisson's Ratio XY	0.27			
13	Poisson's Ratio YZ	0.4			
14	Poisson's Ratio XZ	0.27			
15	Shear Modulus XY	4700	MPa		
16	Shear Modulus YZ	3100	MPa		
17	Shear Modulus XZ	4700	MPa		
18	Orthotropic Stress Limits				
19	Tensile X direction	1685	MPa		
20	Tensile Y direction	20	MPa		
21	Tensile Z direction	20	MPa		

Details

■ Finite element analysis boundary condition setting of π -beam

Schematic of Pull-off Joint Test

Boundary condition of Pull-off

Schematic of Bending Test

Boundary condition of Bending

Details

■ Improvement of beam fabrication

▪ Vacuum infusion process

▪ Improvement of fabrication process

Conventional Vacuum Infusion Molding

- Corner part Low pressure
- The resin flow direction is uneven

(Quality problem) → **Process needs improvement**

Double vacuum bag infusion process

- Maintain vertical shape with external jig
- Additional pressure in double vacuum

Details

▣ π -beam fabrication and evaluation

▪ Specimen by Beam Parameter Condition

	Support Ply	Base Ply	T1:T2 Ratio	Specimen	Section
S2 (Case 2)	2	10	1:6		
S4 (Case 4)	4	6	1:2.5		
S6 (Case 6)	6	2	1:1.3		

- Specification : ASTM STP 1383
- Material : Carbon fabric UD & Vinylester
- Fiber Volume fraction : 55 ~ 57% (ASTM D3171)

Details

▣ π -beam fabrication and evaluation

- Pull-off Joint Test & Beam Bending Test

Pull-off Joint Test Device

Beam Bending Test Device

- Verification of finite element analysis results
- Confirm joint properties
- Identify strength and failure behavior

Results

Boundary condition of π -beam finite element analysis

Pull-off Joint Test

Total deformation

Stress variation due to load

Beam Bending Test

Total deformation

Stress variation due to load

Results

■ π -beam Maximum stress comparison of Pull-off Joint Test

Comparison graph of stress according to T1: T2 ratio

Stress comparison graph with support length (L) change

- The results of the T-beam analysis according to the ratio of T1: T2 show the highest stress at 1009.5MPa in **Case 6**, and the stress tends to increase gradually as the thickness of Pi Support increases after Case 3 (1: 3.7)
- Most of the load is distributed in the Pi base of the π -beam and in the joining area, which confirms that the change of the Pi support length (L) does not have a great effect on the total stress change of the π -beam

Results

■ π -beam Maximum stress comparison of Beam Bending Test

Comparison graph of stress according to T1: T2 ratio

Stress comparison graph with support length (L) change

- T1: Bending test according to T2 ratio π -beam analysis shows the highest stress at 899.25MPa in case 6, and the tendency of increasing stress with increasing thickness of support part after Case 3 (1: 3.7) Indicates
- Pi Support Length (L) Also Case 6 showed the highest stress. Case 3 (L = 30) and Case 4 (L = 30) were found to have relatively high stresses due to the highest load distribution on the Insert Plate on Pi Support

Results

■ π -beam test results

■ Pull-off Joint Test

■ Beam Bending Test

- Both the direct tensile test and the bending test results of the π -beam show the highest load in Case 6 where the support part (T1) is the thickest
- A similar tendency was observed when the results of the experiments and the analyzes of the cases 2, 4, and 6 were compared
- Since the load distribution is mostly distributed in the joints, when the 3D preform π -beam is manufactured, it is possible to improve the strength efficiently by increasing the thickness of the support part and reinforcing the Pi base.

Conclusion

In this study, finite element analysis and direct tensile test according to parametric conditions were performed for the manufacture of high strength preform π type T-beam. The conclusion is as follows.

- As a result of parameter finite element analysis and direct tensile analysis of π -beam, Case 6 shows the highest stress, and 3D preform π -beam is also expected to show high strength when the ratio of Pi support is increased.
- The finite element analysis of the π -beam is similar to that of the experimental results, and can be used as comparative data on the results of the 3D preform beam
- Double vacuum bag infusion molding improves the molding quality and error, and it can be applied to various types of composite beam structures.
- However, since 3D preforms are also woven in the thickness direction, additional studies on 3D preform π -beams and comparison with 2D π -beams are necessary.